

Deliverable D3.3

FEDERATED SIGNAL PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS FUNCTIONS

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PHEMS – Pediatric Hospitals as European drivers for multi-party computation and synthetic data generation capabilities across clinical specialties and data types (Project 101094195)

1. Purpose of the document

This deliverable describes how federated signal processing functions are implemented within the PHEMS architecture to support the clinical use cases. We present a practical example of how a machine learning task for sepsis prediction (Use Case 2) can be executed in a federated learning setting using a PyTorch plug-in.

2. List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AUC-ROC	Area Under the Curve - Receiver Operating Characteristic
AUROC	Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve
CDM	Common Data Model
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment
CO	Confidential (Deliverable Dissemination Level)
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DP	Differential Privacy
FA	Federated Analytics
FedAvg	Federated Averaging (an aggregation algorithm)
FL	Federated Learning
FSJD	Hospital Sant Joan de Déu
GitOps	Git-based operations and deployment model
GOSH	Great Ormond Street Hospital
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
HUS	Helsinki University Hospital
ICD-10	International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision
ICU	Intensive Care Unit
ML	Machine Learning
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
OMOP-CDM	OMOP Common Data Model
PICU	Pediatric Intensive Care Unit
PR	Pull Request
PR-AUC	Precision-Recall Area Under Curve
SMPC	Secure Multi-Party Computation
SQL	Structured Query Language
TF-IDF	Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency
UC	Use Case

3. PHEMS federation architecture

The technical design and components of the PHEMS federation architecture are explained in detail in *Deliverable D2.1: Federation Architecture*. Section 3 of *D2.1* outlines the core architectural components, consisting of: Data Layer, Processing Layer, Control Layer, and Security & Governance Layer. This section provides a high-level summary relevant to the development and deployment of federated signal processing and analysis functions within this ecosystem.

3.1. Data Layer

This layer hosts the harmonized clinical data structured according to the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM). Each hospital retains local control over its data, which is stored in a private PostgreSQL database or similar OMOP-compatible system. The use of OMOP ensures semantic interoperability across sites and enables consistent querying and analysis logic.

3.2. Processing Layer

The processing layer enables local execution of analytics or machine learning tasks. It relies on a containerized environment where jobs can be deployed securely to each federated node. This layer supports both:

- Federated Analytics (FA) — local descriptive statistics, cohort filtering, and aggregation.
- Federated Learning (FL) — distributed model training where no patient-level data leaves the institution.

Containerized tools execute queries and model code locally, accessing OMOP-CDM data directly through secure interfaces.

3.3. Control Layer

The control layer handles task orchestration, coordination and monitoring, including

- Receiving and distributing tasks from the central platform to selected nodes.
- Tracking task execution and status.
- Enforcing review procedures before code is run and before results are released.

This layer plays a central role in supporting GitOps workflows, where task containers are version-controlled and deployed through CI/CD pipelines.

3.4. Security & Governance Layer

This layer ensures that the entire federation operates under strict privacy and governance constraints. Key features include:

- Access control and role-based permissions.
- Task and result review mechanisms enforced locally.
- Audit trails for every job and data access event.
- Secure communication between nodes and central components.

Each data controller maintains authority over which tasks are allowed to run and what results can be shared.

4. Use case specific requirements

4.1. Use Case 1

Use Case 1 (Cardiology patients' operation benchmarking) involves benchmarking and monitoring cardiac care pathways across several pediatric hospitals. The objective is to enable clinicians and data analysts to compute cohort-level statistics and compare aggregated outcomes (e.g., such as treatment durations, diagnostic timelines, and postoperative outcomes), without moving patient-level data.

Technically, this is achieved through the federated analytics layer of the PHEMS architecture, where containerized SQL-based analytics tasks are executed locally on each data controllers' OMOP-mapped datasets. Aggregate results are returned to the user. This workflow has already been demonstrated as a minimum viable product (MVP) in *Deliverable D2.3*, confirming the viability of federated analytics using containerized queries and secure task orchestration.

Looking ahead, custom dashboards will be developed to visualize these federated analytics outputs in a user-friendly way. These dashboards will be developed using R and RShiny. While the dashboard itself will be custom-built, it will leverage existing open-source packages from the OHDSI community for data wrangling and cohort-based analytics.

4.2. Use Cases 2 and 3

In contrast, Use Cases 2 and 3 focus on the development and evaluation of federated machine learning models across hospital sites. Use Case 2 addresses early sepsis prediction in pediatric intensive care units (PICUs), requiring the training of time-sensitive models on physiological and clinical time-series data. Use Case 3 centers on hemophilia, aiming to leverage distributed datasets to improve prediction, patient stratification, and treatment outcome modeling.

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From a technical perspective, both use cases involve the distributed execution of model training and inference tasks, where data remains local and only model updates (e.g., gradients or model parameters) are exchanged. This introduces the need for multi-round orchestration, and more complex aggregation mechanisms. These requirements go beyond simple data querying and demand processing tools capable of supporting stateful training workflows, and synchronization across multiple nodes.

4.3. Learnings from the Sepsis Hackathon (UC2)

In January 2025, we conducted a hackathon focused on early sepsis prediction using pediatric ICU data (<https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/phems-hackathon-early-sepsis-prediction>). The goal was to gain insight into the types of machine learning models that perform best on this clinical problem, and better understand the challenges associated with real-world ICU data, such as temporal irregularities, missing values, and severe class imbalance.

The data used for the competition originated from a single hospital (FSJD) and was not distributed across sites. As such, all model development took place in a centralized setting. Nevertheless, the lessons learned provide guidance for future implementation in a federated setting (ML libraries needed, aggregation algorithms, etc.).

Participants experimented with a variety of modeling strategies, preprocessing pipelines, and evaluation techniques. Results revealed that high-performing models depend on a combination of robust feature engineering, imbalance-aware training, and careful model selection. *CatBoost* emerged as a top performer, particularly when using automatic class weighting to handle the severe label imbalance common in sepsis prediction tasks. Feature engineering approaches like rolling window statistics for time-series vitals and *TF-IDF* (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) encoding of drug exposure patterns proved critical for extracting meaningful clinical signals. Manual resampling techniques were less effective, and hyperparameter tuning—using tools like *Optuna*—played a key role in optimizing model performance.

In a federated learning context, these findings highlight the importance of establishing locally consistent feature engineering pipelines, node-specific class balancing, and ensuring support for gradient boosting frameworks that can function under distributed, privacy-preserving constraints. Additionally, model aggregation strategies will need to account for data heterogeneity and class imbalance across sites, to ensure that global model updates remain stable and clinically relevant.

4.4. Summary of features and requirements

The table below outlines the key features and requirements necessary to implement each use case in a federated context.

Requirements	Use Case 1: Cardiac Benchmarking (FA)	Use Case 2: Sepsis Prediction (FL)	Use Case 3: Haematology / Haemophilia (FL)
Data Format	OMOP-CDM	OMOP-CDM	OMOP-CDM
Processing Type	Federated Analytics	Federated Learning	Federated Learning
Job Type	SQL/statistical tasks	Multi-round ML model training	Multi-round ML model training
Feature Engineering	Filtering, aggregation, cohort definitions	Time-series (e.g., rolling windows), TF-IDF, etc.	Stratification features, longitudinal transformations
Model Types	N/A	Gradient boosting (e.g., CatBoost), possibly LSTM or shallow neural nets	Tree-based models, clustering, regression or classification
Libraries	SQL, R, Python (Pandas, NumPy)	PyTorch, CatBoost, scikit-learn (via PyTorch plug-in); optionally XGBoost or LightGBM	PyTorch, scikit-learn, optionally statistical modeling frameworks
Orchestration Model	One-pass task execution	Multi-round FL with task re-submission	Same as UC2
Aggregation Algorithm	Mean, sum, count (central aggregation of descriptive stats)	FedAvg or weighted FedAvg; support for adaptive or performance-aware aggregation	Same as UC2
Aggregation Payload	Aggregated results (counts, means, medians)	Model weights, gradients, or optimizer states (depending on algorithm)	Same as UC2
Governance Checks	PR-based code review, result approval by data controllers	Same as UC1, with additional scrutiny on model code and returned updates	Same as UC2
Output Type	Aggregated metrics and interactive dashboards for cohort comparison	Trained models, AUROC, PR-AUC, logs, metadata	Same as UC2
Execution Environment	Containerized SQL runners or notebooks	Containerized PyTorch-based training tasks executed via GitOps on each Federated Node	Same as UC2
Update Frequency	On-demand	Iterative / epoch-based	Iterative / epoch-based
Initial Model Sharing	Not applicable	Yes – model architecture and weights shared as part of task PR	Yes – initial model structure and weights shared in PR or config

4.5. Review of open-source FL frameworks

We have already conducted a review of open-source federated learning frameworks, which is detailed in *Deliverable D3.6: Guidance on Statistical Learning Methodologies*. This evaluation assessed several tools across key dimensions critical to the PHEMS context, including:

- Compatibility with OMOP-CDM.
- Support for different FL paradigms: horizontal, vertical, and transfer learning.
- Built-in privacy-preserving mechanisms, such as Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC), Differential Privacy (DP), and Homomorphic Encryption (HE).
- Machine learning library support, including PyTorch and TensorFlow.
- Ease of deployment, especially in containerized environments using Docker and Kubernetes.

As part of this assessment, the following frameworks were deployed to a representative environment for testing:

- Biomed
- MLFlow
- NVIDIA FLARE
- Substra

In addition, we reviewed the documentation and design principles of other relevant frameworks. Based on this analysis, we concluded that integrating a complete machine learning framework into the existing PHEMS architecture would significantly increase its complexity. In many cases, we would not be able to use the orchestration features of these frameworks, as they are not compatible with the PHEMS network design, which only permits outbound connections from secure data environments (i.e. hospital-based federated nodes).

5. Proposed PyTorch implementation

Given the abovementioned constraints, we believe that the most effective approach is to develop a custom PyTorch plug-in for the PHEMS Federated Node which would allow us to support federated machine learning while maintaining compatibility with the existing GitOps and Kubernetes-based infrastructure, described in Deliverable 2.1 and 2.3. This approach offers several benefits:

- Full compatibility with OMOP-CDM data structure and querying logic.
- Support for horizontal, vertical, and transfer learning configurations.
- The potential integration of privacy-preserving mechanisms.
- Deployment in containerized environments (Docker/Kubernetes), consistent with the PHEMS GitOps architecture.

PyTorch is an open-source machine learning and deep learning framework developed by Meta AI. It is built primarily in Python and C++, offering both high-level usability and low-level performance. PyTorch is widely adopted in both academia and industry due to its intuitive syntax, dynamic computation graphs, and strong community ecosystem. PyTorch is compatible with a wide array of machine learning libraries and algorithms. This includes not only deep learning models, but also integration with external libraries such as *CatBoost*, *LightGBM*, *XGBoost*, and *scikit-learn*, which are essential for building robust and efficient models. These libraries cover a broad spectrum of ML paradigms: gradient boosting, decision trees, logistic regression, support vector machines, clustering methods, and dimensionality reduction techniques. These tools offer high flexibility for selecting and tuning the most appropriate algorithm for the PHEMS use cases.

5.1. General workflow of the FA/FL architecture

Tasks are defined via GitHub pull request (PR), reviewed by data controllers, approved, and executed on the corresponding hospital's Federated Node. This same architecture can be used for the signal processing and machine learning tasks envisioned for Use Cases 2 and 3, through the integration of the PyTorch plug-in. Development of this plug-in is scheduled to begin in the second half of 2025. This implementation will differ from the standard analytics tasks in Deliverable 2.3 in several aspects:

- The machine learning model will be stored in a location accessible to the Federated Node, allowing it to be deployed alongside the data.
- The PR process will be used to specify the model architecture, initial weights, and relevant training parameters.
- Upon PR approval, the model and configuration will be pulled into the data controller's Federated Node and executed securely.
- Once training is completed, updated model weights (or results) will be pushed back to the GitHub repository or another secure environment specified by the data controller.

1	User initiates task in Github
2	ArgoCD pipeline detects task
3	Task is initiated on Federated Node
4a	HUS – task results are returned to Github
4b	GOSH – task results are returned to workspace

5.2. Example workflow for UC2

This section outlines a practical example of how a machine learning model for early sepsis detection can be developed and executed in a federated learning setting using the PHEMS infrastructure and the PyTorch plug-in.

5.2.1. Step 1: Develop the model code and feature pipeline

In the researcher's local development environment, the ML pipeline is implemented using PyTorch, with a focus on early sepsis prediction based on OMOP-CDM-mapped ICU data. The pipeline includes:

- Query logic to extract relevant time-series data from OMOP-CDM tables.
- Feature engineering, such as:
 - E.g., Rolling mean and standard deviation over 3h/6h windows for vitals (e.g., heart rate, temperature).

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- Model definition, using *CatBoost* or a PyTorch-based classifier with class weighting to address imbalance.
- Training loop with loss function and optimizer. Training pipelines should support multi-epoch local training, particularly for gradient boosting or shallow neural network models suited to ICU data. Time-sensitive signals such as rolling vitals and lab trends require sufficient training depth to be captured effectively.
- Evaluation metrics, including AUROC, PR-AUC, and time-to-positive prediction windows.

5.2.2. Step 2: Containerize the task

- A Dockerfile is written and:
 - Installs all dependencies (PyTorch, SQLAlchemy, Pandas, etc.).
 - Includes the training script.
 - Configures access to local OMOP-CDM via environment variables or config file.
- The container is built and pushed to a secure container registry.

5.2.3. Step 3: Prepare the GitHub Pull Request

- The researcher creates a new PR in the PHEMS GitHub repository with:
 - A reference to the Docker image (with version tag).
 - Metadata (e.g., participating hospitals, training window, model type).
 - Initial model weights (optional).
 - A configuration YAML/JSON that specifies training parameters.
- This PR defines the full job to be executed within each Federated Node.

5.2.4. Step 4: Task review and approval

- Every new training task must be submitted as a GitHub PR and undergoes a mandatory code review by data controllers at each participating hospital. The review includes:
 - SQL query logic and data access scope.
 - Model architecture and training configuration.
 - Aggregation and evaluation methods.
- Once approved, the container is permitted to run on local data. If the same code is reused for subsequent rounds (e.g., in a multi-round training task), re-approval is not required unless the container or logic changes. However, any changes to the codebase, query scope, or model parameters trigger a new PR and review cycle.

5.2.5. Step 5: Local task execution

Inside the secure environment of each hospital's Federated Node, the container executes:

- Connects to the local OMOP-CDM database.
- Extracts and preprocesses data.
- Trains the local sepsis prediction model.
- Stores updated model weights and evaluation metrics.
- Execution is isolated and logged for auditability.

5.2.6. Step 6: Results return and aggregation

After local training (spanning multiple epochs), each node returns model updates such as weights or gradients. Before these are shared:

- The local results are reviewed by the data controller to ensure they comply with output governance rules (e.g., no sensitive values or patient counts).
- If approved, the updates are aggregated (e.g., using FedAvg), and optionally redistributed for the next training round.

Federated learning for sepsis prediction might require multiple training rounds, especially for time-series models. The updated global model is used to re-initiate training at each site, continuing the cycle until convergence or performance goals are met.

5.2.7. Step 7: Final model evaluation and approval

Once all training rounds are complete and the final model is aggregated:

- Each data controller reviews the final model and accompanying evaluation outputs (e.g., AUROC, PR-AUC, calibration plots).
- This review confirms:
 - The final output does not expose sensitive information.
 - The model behaves as expected on local data (optional validation can be run).

5.2.8. Step 8: Result delivery

After final approval:

- The final model, training logs, and evaluation metrics are delivered to the researcher, either:
 - In a secure workspace or
 - Through another platform agreed upon by the data controllers.

6. Conclusion

This deliverable outlines the technical approach for implementing federated signal processing and analysis functions within the current PHEMS architecture.

Use Case 1 has already demonstrated the viability of federated analytics through an MVP implementation, where containerized analytical tasks were successfully executed on the GOSH and HUS environments, and aggregated results were returned securely. For Use Cases 2 and 3, federated learning will be implemented through a PyTorch plug-in. This approach enables multi-round model training and supports complex ML workflows such as time-sensitive sepsis prediction.

The implementation of this framework will begin in June 2025. For successful testing and validation of the proposed framework, it is important that all data controllers finalize their deployment of the FN and participate in the current MVP infrastructure. This will enable early testing of UC2 and UC3 in realistic settings with datasets from all data controllers. In turn, this will help to reveal implementation gaps and help to optimize this framework before a full-scale deployment in late 2025.

<https://docs.pytorch.org/docs/stable/index.html>

<https://pytorch.org/projects/pytorch/>